

1 Landscape management can foster pollinator richness in fragmented high-
2 value habitats

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10

11 Abstract

12 Pollinator diversity is declining due to habitat loss, low habitat quality, limited habitat connectivity and
13 intensification of agriculture in remaining high-value habitats within human-dominated landscapes,
14 such as calcareous grasslands. Options to increase local area of protected habitats are often limited.
15 Therefore, we asked how local habitat quality as well as agri-environmental schemes (AES) and
16 configuration of the surrounding landscape can contribute to the preservation of pollinator diversity.
17 We sampled bees, butterflies, and hoverflies in 40 calcareous grasslands in Germany and assessed the
18 effects of calcareous grassland area, quality and connectivity, agricultural configuration, and AES on
19 species richness and abundance. While calcareous grassland area was an important predictor for bee
20 and butterfly species richness, with strongest effects sizes for endangered species, local flower
21 resources and nesting sites and landscape characteristics such as small field size, high proportion of
22 organic fields and connectivity with other grasslands significantly enhanced pollinator richness with
23 responses differing among the three studied taxa. In contrast to expectation AES flowering fields did
24 not benefit pollinator communities in grasslands. We conclude that improving local habitat quality in
25 combination with targeted landscape management are effective measures to promote pollinator
26 richness in highly fragmented protected grassland.

27 **Keywords:** wild pollinators, calcareous grassland, habitat area, agri-environmental schemes, landscape
28 management, nature conservation

29 1. Introduction

30 Habitat loss and land-use change are the main drivers of the rapid decline of insects in recent decades
31 [1–3]. The loss of wild pollinating insects in particular, poses a serious threat to humanity and nature,
32 as 35% of crops[4] and about 88% of all angiosperms worldwide benefit from pollination by insects or
33 other animals [5]. In Central Europe, semi-natural habitats like calcareous grasslands are major
34 remaining refuges for wild pollinators in human-dominated agricultural landscapes. Crop fields alone
35 are unlikely to fulfil the actual needs of pollinators whereas calcareous grasslands are valuable habitats
36 because of their ability to provide a variety of floral resources and nesting sites [6,7]. The low
37 disturbance intensity of these grasslands allows many pollinators, including many endangered species,
38 to survive and provide pollination services to adjacent crop fields [8,9]. Calcareous grasslands were
39 once an integral part of the landscape, and were created by extensive grazing. However, due to the
40 unprofitability of extensive farming and the continued agricultural intensification, calcareous
41 grasslands have become increasingly fragmented and isolated [10].

42 Through the lens of island biogeographic [11] and ecosystem decay theory [12], the decreasing area of
43 calcareous grasslands should be accompanied by a loss of within-patch biodiversity and habitat quality,
44 including floral and nesting resources. The positive effect of habitat area [13,14] and flower resources
45 on pollinators has been shown frequently [15,16]. However, nesting resources are also important for
46 wild bees, but this driver has rarely been studied, and even more rarely in combination with calcareous
47 grassland area and floral resources in the context of grasslands [17,18]. Above the scale of a single
48 patch, the proportion of calcareous grasslands in the landscape is expected to affect pollinator
49 diversity by determining habitat connectivity [17,19]. The positive effects of a higher cover and
50 connectivity of calcareous grasslands could be due to more abundant, diverse, and temporally
51 continuous floral resources. Additionally, the higher probability of dispersal events in a well-connected
52 metacommunity decreases the risk of populations becoming extinct in fragmented habitats [20].

53 To reach other calcareous grassland fragments, pollinators often have to cross the surrounding
54 agricultural matrix. However, it is unclear how hostile this matrix is to pollinators found on protected
55 grasslands [21,22]. In addition, it is difficult in practice to foster pollinators by increasing calcareous
56 grassland and improving habitat connectivity, as land is a valuable commodity, and much land is
57 already under cultivation. Therefore, a comparison between the classically considered variables of
58 calcareous grassland area and connectivity and the changes that can be achieved through land
59 management is desirable and has not been widely studied. Pollinators often use flower resources in
60 agricultural fields and adjacent perennial habitats [23,24], but it has rarely been studied how the
61 composition and configuration of the agricultural matrix contributes to pollinator diversity in grassland
62 patches. Smaller crop fields in the surrounding landscape, for instance can lead to higher structural

63 and vegetative diversity, as more crop edges lead to the presence of uncultivated field margins and
64 hedgerows [25](The lower management intensity of field edges leads to reduced use of fertilizers and
65 insecticides, which can support higher levels of flower density and pollinator colonization in field edges
66 compared to centers [26](. This together could result in more area that provides food and nesting
67 resources [27,28]. Another approach to enhance agricultural land for biodiversity is through agri-
68 environmental schemes (AES), such as organic farming and flowering fields. Both AES are expected to
69 benefit pollinators on calcareous grasslands because the absence of pesticides in organically managed
70 fields and the establishment of flowering fields lead to a higher floral cover [29,30] and improve
71 connectivity at the landscape scale [31,32]. However, there are only a few studies focusing on
72 landscape-scale effects of organic farming [30,33] and knowledge about the effect of AES on
73 pollinators in high-value habitats is lacking.

74 This study assesses the effects of calcareous grassland area and quality, habitat connectivity,
75 agricultural landscape configuration and AES, on wild bee, butterfly and hoverfly species richness and
76 abundance in calcareous grasslands. Consistent with the island biogeographic and ecosystem decay
77 theory, we expect that (1) pollinator species richness and abundance will increase with calcareous
78 grassland area and connectivity, as well as with patch-scale habitat quality. With respect to the
79 agricultural matrix, (2) smaller field sizes in the surrounding landscape should lead to higher pollinator
80 species richness and abundance on calcareous grasslands through more small-structured crop edges.
81 In addition, the presence of AES like organic farming and flowering fields should increase pollinator
82 species richness and abundance by augmenting food resources on the landscape scale.

83 2. Methods

84 2.1. Study region and sampling sites

85 The study was conducted in 2022 across two study regions in Northern Bavaria, Germany: Lower
86 Franconia and Upper Franconia (Figure 1). The two regions differ in their annual mean temperature of
87 2022 (11.06° C in Lower and 10.29° C in Upper Franconia), annual precipitation 2022 (565.6 mm in Lower
88 and 698.8 mm in Upper Franconia), and altitude (284 m above sea level (asl) in Lower and 465 m asl in
89 Upper Franconia) [34–36]. The geology of Lower Franconia is characterized by shell limestone whereas
90 Jurassic limestone is dominant in Upper Franconia [37]. In both regions calcareous grasslands were
91 formerly widespread on slopes of the valleys [38] and are nowadays embedded in an agricultural
92 matrix characterised by annual crop fields and, especially in Lower Franconia, vineyards.

93 Forty calcareous grasslands (20 grasslands per study region) were selected as study sites to test the
94 effects of local and landscape variables on wild pollinator species richness and abundance, and flower
95 resources. To cover a broad gradient of local and landscape variables, study sites were selected with

196 different habitat areas (ranging from 0.07 ha to 31.54 ha), and different habitat connectivity, measured
 197 as the proportion of calcareous grasslands in a buffer with 2 km radius around the study sites (ranging
 198 from 0% to 4.7%) excluding the study site area. Distance between study sites was always at least 2 km
 199 to ensure independent landscapes and species communities.

100
 101 *Figure 1. Locations of the forty study sites (calcareous grasslands) in two study regions: Lower (red) and Upper*
 102 *Franconia (yellow) (A, B). Map source: Corine Landcover 2018 © GeoBasis-DE / BKG (2023). Calcareous grassland*
 103 *in Upper Franconia (C). Visualization of variable transect walks for bees, hoverflies, and butterflies on a calcareous*
 104 *grassland in Upper Franconia (D).*

105 2.2. Wild pollinators

106 Bees (Hymenoptera: Apiformes), hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae), butterflies (Lepidoptera:
 107 Hesperioidea and Papilionoidea) and burnet moths (Lepidoptera: Zygaenidae) were sampled on the
 108 study sites five times from April to August 2022. In the following, butterflies always include burnet
 109 moths. We analyzed bumblebees separately from other wild bees, as bumblebees differ from other
 110 bees in their ecology and sociality, and we omitted honeybees altogether. In the following, the term
 111 solitary bees refers to all bees except bumblebees and honey bees, and includes solitary bees as well

112 as primitively eusocial halictid bees. The order of study sites visited was randomized for each sampling
113 round. In order to sample bees, hoverflies and butterflies, variable transect walks with no fixed
114 direction were carried out (Figure 1). Transects were not a straight line but were directed in parts of
115 the study site representative and attractive for wild pollinators i.e., flower patches and bare ground
116 slopes. Transect location could change from round to round and between bee/hoverfly and butterfly
117 sampling. Transect length for bees and hoverflies was 750 m and transect width was 2 m resulting in
118 1500 m² transect area regardless of study site area. Transect length for butterflies was 900 m and
119 transect width was 5 m resulting in 4500 m² transect area to account for higher mobility of butterflies.
120 Transect time was 45 minutes. Sampling was conducted from 9 am to 5 pm during suitable weather
121 conditions (temperatures above 13° C in the sun, low wind (<3 bft), and no rain). Each study site was
122 sampled at least once in the morning, in the noon and in the afternoon and changed from round to
123 round. One single person carried out collections and taxonomic identification in the field for bees and
124 hoverflies and another person for butterflies. Wild pollinators were caught with a net if not identified
125 on the wing. Wild pollinators which couldn't be identified to species level in the field were collected
126 and identified in the laboratory; otherwise, the pollinator was released after identification. Bumblebee
127 queens were not collected and were identified to species level in the field. Bee and butterfly species
128 were classified as endangered or not endangered according to the Red List of Bavaria [39]. Too few
129 endangered hoverfly and bumblebee species were sampled to warrant a separate analysis of these
130 taxa. Pollinator species richness and abundance were pooled across rounds. Due to the equal sampling
131 size in time and area on all study sites, pollinator species richness is equivalent to species density per
132 transect and pollinator abundance is equivalent to population density per transect, rather than the
133 total species number or total abundance of the calcareous grassland fragment. Following frequently
134 used terminology including recent studies [12,40,41] we use the terms species richness and abundance
135 throughout the manuscript.

136 2.3. Local and landscape variables

137 To estimate the influence of local variables, we used calcareous grassland area and habitat quality,
138 consisting of the variables flower richness, flower cover and nesting sites on the transects. Calcareous
139 grassland area is the area of the sampled calcareous grassland fragment and was calculated in Esri
140 ArcGIS Pro using satellite and aerial imagery from the layer "World Imagery" [42]. As a measure of
141 flower richness, each flowering plant species was recorded during the transect walk for each sampling
142 round and for bee/hoverfly and butterfly transect separately. Flower cover on the transect was
143 estimated for all flowering vascular plants in cm² and then converted to percent cover. Nesting sites is
144 the estimated percentage of the cover of potential nesting sites for solitary bees on the transect.
145 Potential nesting sites for ground-nesting solitary bees are slopes with open ground, loamy sandy spots
146 [43,44] whereas above-ground-nesting bees rely on i.e. dead wood and hollow stems [45]. Suitable

147 open soil spots and the surface of dead wood were estimated in m² and then converted in percent
148 cover. Flower resources, but not nesting resources were correlated with calcareous grassland area.
149 Flower richness, flower cover and nesting sites were averaged for each plot across rounds.

150 Landscape variables were calculated within a 2 km radius around the study site centre, to estimate the
151 influence of landscape composition and configuration. The landscape analysis was conducted within
152 the 2 km radius because it represents a reasonable pollinator foraging and dispersal range [19,46–48].
153 To analyse the influence of habitat connectivity on wild pollinator species richness and abundance, the
154 total amount of calcareous grasslands in the surrounding landscape excluding the study site area itself
155 was calculated. To test the influence of the surrounding landscape configuration on wild pollinators in
156 calcareous grasslands, percentage cover of annual crop fields (excluding leys) and mean field size of
157 annual crop fields in hectares were calculated, as a measure of intensity and diversity of the agricultural
158 matrix. As small fields have a higher proportion of edges than large fields and lower management
159 intensity in field edges compared to field centres, smaller fields are expected to lead to more food and
160 nesting resources for pollinators at the landscape scale. In order to understand if and how agri-
161 environmental schemes promote wild pollinators in protected grasslands, the two best-known and -
162 established AES were quantified: the percentage cover of organic farming and flowering fields in
163 relation to the total annual crop cover. Organic farming uses fewer pesticides, provides more non-crop
164 vegetation and a more diverse crop rotation than conventional farming [49]. Flowering fields are
165 likewise financially subsidised measures to increase the food resources and shelter for wild plants and
166 animals in arable farming. Both measures are expected to promote wild pollinators even in calcareous
167 grasslands because they lead to a higher flower cover at the landscape scale [29,30]. The calculation
168 of landscape variables was done in ArcGIS Pro 2.2.0 [50]. Aerial photos [42] and data from the biotope
169 mapping Bavaria (Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt 2021, www.lfu.bayern.de) and the integrated
170 management and control system for Bavarian agriculture (InVeKos, Bayerische Landesanstalt für
171 Landwirtschaft 2022) showing detailed information about land use classes, field crops and agri-
172 environmental schemes from 2022 were used.

173 2.4. Statistical analysis

174 We used structural causal modelling to design statistical models to estimate the causal effects of local
175 and landscape variables on pollinator species richness and abundance. Briefly, we constructed a
176 directed acyclic graph (DAG) expressing plausible causal relations among our variables (Figure 2), then
177 identified via the back door criterion sets of covariates needed to obtain an unbiased estimate of the
178 causal effect of each explanatory variable [51]. To ensure the appropriateness of the DAG, we tested
179 the DAG-data consistency. We show that our DAG contains no open biasing paths, and all implied
180 independencies are consistent with the observational dataset. We also tested the variables in our DAG

181 for residual spatial autocorrelation using the DHARMA Morans I test for distance-based autocorrelation
 182 and for multicollinearity using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). Despite the advantages of DAGs,
 183 possible limitations of the approach are that DAGs build on assumptions based on domain knowledge,
 184 literature and the experience of researchers to explain the studied system. The DAG can therefore help
 185 to understand complex ecological processes, but there is no guarantee that all assumptions are correct
 186 [51]. More details about DAG construction, validation and possible limitations can be found in the
 187 supplementary material (Supplementary Methods S1).

188
 189 *Figure 2. Directed acyclic graph (DAG) showing the causal structure (arrows) among local, landscape and regional*
 190 *variables (rectangles) hypothesized to be driving wild pollinator species richness and abundance (oval). MAT =*
 191 *mean annual temperature.*

192 The effects of local and landscape variables on pollinator species richness and abundance and flower
 193 resources were estimated using generalized linear models (GLM). Response variables were pollinator
 194 species richness and abundance, with separate models fitted for each pollinator group and, in the case
 195 of bees and butterflies, for endangered species. Local explanatory variables were flower richness and
 196 flower cover for bees/hoverflies and butterflies respectively, nesting sites for solitary bees and
 197 calcareous grassland area. Grassland area was log₁₀-transformed to increase linearity. Explanatory
 198 landscape variables were habitat connectivity, mean field size, cover of organic farming, cover of
 199 flowering fields, and annual crop cover. At the regional level, we included mean annual temperature
 200 (1970 – 2010) as well as the region identity (Upper vs. Lower Franconia). Models were fitted using a
 201 Poisson distribution for pollinator species richness and a negative binomial distribution (to correct
 202 over-dispersion) for pollinator abundance. Obtaining unbiased causal estimates for each variable of
 203 interest required fitting separate models for local- and landscape-level inferences, since the effects of

204 landscape are partially mediated by local conditions. We also included models in which flower cover
205 and richness were response variables explained by the other explanatory variables. The generalized
206 linear model to analyse the effect of calcareous grassland area and landscape variables was: $x \sim$
207 calcareous grassland area + habitat connectivity + mean field size + organic farming + flowering fields
208 + annual crop cover + mean annual temperature + region. The generalized linear model to analyse the
209 effect of habitat quality was: $x \sim$ calcareous grassland area + habitat connectivity + mean field size +
210 organic farming + flowering fields + annual crop cover + flower richness + flower cover + nesting sites
211 + mean annual temperature + region. The variables included in the models were tested for residual
212 spatial autocorrelation and multicollinearity, and no correlations ($p > 0.05$) were identified.

213 The statistical analyses were performed using the software R v 4.3.1 and RStudio v 2023.06.1 [52]. The
214 package *tidyverse* [53] was used for data handling. GLMs with negative binomial distribution were
215 performed using the package *MASS* [54]. The packages *dagitty* [55], *DHARMA* [56], *car* [57], *ncf* [58]
216 and *performance* [59] were used for model validation. The packages *marginaleffects* [60] and
217 *modelsummary* [61] were used to derive marginal effects of the GLMs. All graphs were generated using
218 R packages *ggplot2* [62] and *ggeffects* [63]. A complete description and reproducible workflow for
219 model fitting, validation, and visualization is provided in the supplementary material S1.

220 3. Results

221 In total, we recorded 231 wild bee species and 10,859 wild bee individuals (of which 21 were
222 bumblebee species and 2,830 bumblebee individuals), 90 butterfly species (24,917 butterfly
223 individuals), 62 hoverfly species (1,524 hover fly individuals) and 274 flowering plant species on the 40
224 calcareous grasslands (see Figure S3 for species richness and abundance data among sites). We
225 detected 44% of all wild bees known from Bavaria, 48% of butterflies, and 16% of hoverflies.
226 Furthermore, 23% of the sampled wild bee species, 33% of butterfly species and 3% of hoverfly species
227 were endangered according to the Red List of Bavaria.

228 3.1. Local effects

229 Calcareous grassland area had the strongest effect on solitary bees, butterflies, and flower resources.
230 A tenfold increase in calcareous grassland area resulted in an increase in species richness of solitary
231 bees, endangered solitary bees, butterflies and endangered butterflies by 12.6%, 28%, 17.9% and
232 52.5%, respectively. Furthermore, flower richness and cover of the studied calcareous grasslands
233 increased with increasing area (Figure 3, Figure 4). However, calcareous grassland area had no
234 significant effect on hoverflies and bumblebees (Table S1).

235
 236 *Figure 3. Coefficient estimates and 95% confidence intervals of GLMs analysing the effect of local variables*
 237 *(calcareous grassland area (log10-transformed), flower richness, flower cover (log10-transformed), nesting sites)*
 238 *and landscape variables (habit connectivity, mean field size, organic farming, and flowering fields) on pollinator*
 239 *species richness and abundance. Black coefficient estimates and confidence intervals indicate significant results*
 240 *($p < 0.05$). Parameter estimates have been back-transformed from log-link-scale to the response scale that is why*
 241 *the estimates change around 1 and not 0.*

242 Habitat quality affected solitary bees, butterflies, and hoverflies. An increasing proportional amount
 243 of potential nesting sites had a positive effect on solitary bee species richness and abundance. With
 244 additional 5% of the transect area covered with potential nesting sites, 18% more solitary bee species
 245 are expected. Endangered solitary bees were not significantly affected by the proportional amount of
 246 potential nesting sites (Table S1). Hoverfly species richness and abundance increased with increasing
 247 flower richness. Flower cover had a significant positive effect on butterfly abundance (Figure 3, Figure
 248 4).

249 **3.2. Landscape effects**

250 Habitat connectivity, i.e. the total amount of calcareous grassland in the surrounding landscape buffer
 251 excluding the study site area itself, affected endangered butterfly species and flower resources on
 252 calcareous grasslands positively. If habitat connectivity was increased because calcareous grasslands
 253 covered an additional one percent of the landscape buffer, endangered butterfly species increased by
 254 15% and flower richness by 4% (Figure 3, Figure 5)

255
 256 *Figure 4. Relationship between (endangered) solitary bee, bumblebee, (endangered) butterfly, hoverfly species*
 257 *richness and abundance and local variables: calcareous grassland area (log10-transformed), flower richness,*
 258 *flower cover and nesting sites. Only significant results of GLMs are shown ($p < 0.05$). A discrepancy between the*
 259 *regression line and the location of the original observed data points (grey points) is possible because the*
 260 *regression line represents the predicted values that have been adjusted by the covariates in the model, with all*
 261 *covariates set to their mean values. Figure with all sub-plots is shown in the supplementary material (Figure S4).*

262
 263 *Figure 5. Relationship between (endangered) solitary bee, bumblebee, (endangered) butterfly, hoverfly species*
 264 *richness and abundance landscape variables: habitat connectivity, mean field size, organic farming, and flowering*
 265 *fields. Only significant results of GLMs are shown ($p < 0.05$). A discrepancy between the regression line and the*
 266 *location of the original observed data points (grey points) is possible because the regression line represents the*
 267 *predicted values that have been adjusted by the covariates in the model, with all covariates set to their mean*
 268 *values.*

269 The configuration of the agricultural landscape, as a measure of quality of the agricultural matrix,
 270 affected solitary bee abundance: If mean field size of the annual crop fields in the matrix increased by
 271 one hectare, solitary bee abundance decreased by 30%. Pollinator species richness and abundance on
 272 calcareous grasslands of other pollinator groups were not significantly affected by mean field size.
 273 Organic farming, i.e. cover of this AES as a proportion of annual crop fields, had a positive effect on the
 274 abundance of bumblebees and endangered butterflies. If an additional 10% of annual crop fields in the
 275 landscape buffer were managed organically, bumblebee abundance increased by 10% and endangered
 276 butterfly abundance increased by 20%. It should be noted that abundances in this study represent the
 277 density of individuals per 1,500 m² and 4,500 m² for bees/hoverflies and butterflies respectively, from
 278 which the population size for the total grassland fragment can be derived. Flowering fields, i.e. cover
 279 of this AES in proportion to annual crop fields, enhanced flower richness on calcareous grassland. If an
 280 additional 1% of annual crop fields in the landscape buffer was converted to flowering fields, 2% more
 281 flowering plant species were found on calcareous grassland (Figure 3, Figure 5). Organic farming and
 282 flowering fields did not significantly affect pollinator species richness and abundance of other
 283 pollinator groups (Table S1).

284 4. Discussion

285 4.1. Local effects

286 Calcareous grassland area was the strongest predictor of pollinator species richness and thus is in
287 accordance with the species-area-relationship predicted by island biogeographic theory [11]. Large
288 calcareous grasslands promote solitary bees and butterflies [65,66] and endangered species even more
289 since these species are often specialized on one habitat [65,67]. At the local scale, larger fragments
290 reduce the risk of extinction and can provide a larger number of food and nesting resources, enabling
291 the coexistence of more pollinator species and larger, more viable populations [12,66,68]. This also
292 becomes clear through the positive relationship between calcareous grassland area and flower
293 resources in this study. In addition to calcareous grassland area, we found that the percentage cover
294 of potential nesting sites was important for solitary bees [17,18]. This is particularly relevant as most
295 bee species in Central Europe are ground nesting [45], and most of the studied calcareous grasslands
296 are located on slopes and have rocky and sandy soil which are suitable nesting substrates [44].
297 According to our data, already a 5% increase of area providing potential nesting sites increased solitary
298 bee richness by ca. 20%. To achieve the same richness increase based on the species-area-relationship
299 a theoretical thirty times increase of calcareous grassland area would be required, underpinning the
300 value of management options targeted on nesting sites for pollinator conservation. Although
301 calcareous grassland area is the strongest predictor of pollinator species richness and abundance, it is
302 challenging, if not impossible, to expand the size of existing calcareous grasslands. This study indicates
303 that it is not always necessary to increase the calcareous grassland area; rather, improving the quality
304 can be an effective measure. For instance, nesting structures such as open ground and slope edges can
305 be maintained by keeping the area in an open state through mowing, grazing, and preventing scrub
306 encroachment.

307 The positive relationship between flower resources and pollinators on calcareous grasslands also
308 indicates that enhancing the quality of the habitat is a logical course of action when the expansion of
309 calcareous grasslands seems not feasible. Pollinators require nectar and pollen to feed both
310 themselves and their larvae [69,70] and some species are highly restricted in their flower selection
311 [45]. Hence, it is crucial to maintain a high cover of flowers and a diverse range of flowering plant
312 species. This was reflected in the positive relationship between flower cover and butterfly abundance.
313 Recent studies have shown that the availability of flower resources has an impact on the species
314 richness of butterfly [71], solitary bee and bumblebee species [43,72]. However, in our study, solitary
315 bee and butterfly species richness were better explained by calcareous grassland area. In turn,
316 hoverflies benefited from calcareous grasslands through diverse flowering plant species, even when
317 area was held constant. Hoverflies have different requirements than bees and butterflies, i.e. they

318 need a cooler microclimate and their larvae have diverse requirements for their developmental habitat
319 [73], suggesting that hoverflies do not rely on calcareous grasslands themselves but on flower
320 resources and landscape heterogeneity [47,74]. In general, increasing the size of the habitat is still
321 preferable for pollinator protection. In practice, however, this often encounters difficulties. It is then
322 advisable to pay particular attention to habitat quality, as management changes can significantly
323 impact pollinators. However, smaller calcareous grassland areas are often accompanied by lower
324 habitat quality and loss of ecological processes that lead to a more rapid decay of the ecosystem [12].
325 Therefore, where it is not feasible to maintain either calcareous grassland area or quality, the focus of
326 conservation approaches should be beyond local habitats at landscape scales.

327 4.2. Landscape effects

328 Habitat connectivity - measured as the amount of calcareous grasslands at the landscape scale -
329 positively influenced endangered butterfly species. This positive pattern has also been found in other
330 semi-natural grasslands [19,75] and can be explained by increased dispersal of butterflies. Higher
331 colonisation rates reduce the risk of extinction in fragmented habitats [76]. The connectivity effects
332 indicate the importance of immigration for the survival of endangered species. A positive effect of
333 habitat connectivity on flower richness suggests that habitat connectivity enhances seed dispersal and
334 genetic diversity of plants [77]. This, in turn, can promote pollinators in their local habitats by
335 diversifying their food resources.

336 Habitat connectivity may also be important for bees, as the presence of multiple habitat fragments is
337 necessary for their survival as suggested by the meta-population theory [78]. However, in our study
338 region, connectivity was not a limiting factor for solitary bees. Landscape variables regarding
339 agricultural management were more important. Landscapes with smaller crop fields were beneficial
340 for solitary bee abundance, and our data suggest that a reduction of field sizes is an effective measure
341 to promote solitary bees where calcareous grassland area cannot be enlarged. To increase the
342 abundance of solitary bees by 20%, a reduction of the average field size by 0.5 ha is already sufficient,
343 while the calcareous grassland area would have to be six times larger than before to achieve the same
344 effect. It should be noted that the density of bee individuals per transect (1,500 m²) is being discussed
345 here, rather than the total abundance of the calcareous grassland fragment. An increase in calcareous
346 grassland area not only leads to an increase in densities per transect, but also to an increase in
347 population sizes due to the effect of the increase in area alone. The effect achieved by increasing
348 calcareous grassland area is therefore many times greater and should therefore be favoured in nature
349 conservation measures. However, smaller fields result in longer and more edge structures between
350 adjacent annual crop fields [27]. Structures such as field margins, hedgerows, and small open paths
351 provide additional food and nesting resources by having a higher flower cover and experiencing fewer

352 disturbances. Additionally, field edges receive less management intensity than field centers and are
353 therefore better habitats for pollinators. The additional colonisation of plants in the field edges has
354 the effect of an increased food supply. Pollinators also colonise the less intensively managed field
355 edges [26,79]. Field boundaries and edges therefore enhance the presence of food and nesting sites
356 and connectivity since pollinators can more easily move across crop fields [80,81]. This study
357 emphasizes that dividing large crop fields into smaller ones may be an effective approach to benefit
358 solitary bees not only inside the agricultural matrix but even in high-value habitats. This relatively easy-
359 to-implement measure could be accompanied by an establishment of new hedgerows and unmanaged
360 field margins to further increase structural heterogeneity at the landscape scale. Moreover, the study
361 indicates that adaptations in landscape management can have a more pronounced impact than
362 changes in conventional landscape variables, such as calcareous grassland area and connectivity, which
363 are frequently challenging to implement in practice. However, mean field size did not affect
364 bumblebees, hoverflies or butterflies, despite the likelihood of a more structurally diverse agriculture
365 and increasing food and shelter resources resulting from it [82–84].

366 For bumblebees and endangered butterflies on calcareous grasslands, organic farming in the
367 surrounding landscape was found to be a determining factor, likely due to the positive aspects of
368 organic compared to conventional farming. Pollinators are less exposed to insecticides in calcareous
369 grassland adjacent to organic fields [49,85], and reduced herbicide use leads to a higher flower cover
370 of non-crop vegetation in organically managed fields [29]. Bumblebees and endangered butterflies
371 likely benefited from higher floral and larvae plant resources [23,86]. In general, few studies have
372 tested the effect of organic farming on pollinator species richness and abundance at the landscape
373 scale [30]. It is therefore all the more remarkable that this study showed positive effects of organic
374 farming on bumblebees and butterflies in protected high-value habitats. This study also shows that
375 increasing the cover of organic farming can be an effective measure in pollinator conservation where
376 the expansion of calcareous grassland area is not feasible. Our data suggest that there is a 20% increase
377 in endangered butterfly abundance if an additional 10% of the surrounding crop cover is converted to
378 organic farming. To achieve the same result, the calcareous grassland area would have to be 2.25-
379 times larger. As previously stated, these are densities per transect and not total abundances of the
380 grassland fragment. An increase in calcareous grassland area is also associated with an increase in
381 population sizes and, therefore, should be favoured as a measure. For bumblebee abundances, organic
382 farming was the only influencing variable and resulted in a 10% increase in abundances per additional
383 10% of annual crop cover managed organically. Solitary bee abundance was not affected by the cover
384 of organic farming but by mean field size of annual crops in the surrounding landscape, suggesting that
385 for solitary bees in calcareous grasslands, the structure of the agricultural landscape is more important
386 than management type. However, Holzschuh et al. (2008) showed that a high organic land cover in the

387 landscape had a positive impact on wild bee species richness and density in fallow strips due to
388 increased flower resources. While other studies show that AES are not effective for conserving
389 endangered species in crop fields themselves [85,87], our study suggests that organic farming can
390 support endangered butterflies as well as bumblebees on landscape scales and in high-value pollinator
391 habitats.

392 We found no direct effect of flowering fields in the surrounding landscape on pollinator richness or
393 abundance on calcareous grasslands. Recent studies provide evidence for the effectiveness of
394 flowering fields along crop field edges for pollinator species richness and abundance in field edges
395 [31,88]. It becomes clear that flowering fields attract many pollinators and are advantageous
396 compared to other habitats, such as flowerless crop fields. The low gradient of flowering fields in the
397 landscape in our study could explain missing correlations. However, we found a positive effect of
398 flowering fields on flower richness in calcareous grasslands, presumably through seed dispersal,
399 underpinning the importance of using autochthonous origins for seed mixtures. In addition, the seed
400 mixtures eligible for federal funding can contain over 40 plant species, including those found on
401 calcareous grasslands. Therefore, pollinators profit at least indirectly from sown flowering fields in the
402 agricultural landscape. Hoverflies were not influenced by any landscape variable. Since hoverflies are
403 not specialised on calcareous grasslands, heterogeneous landscapes, in general may be more
404 beneficial [74].

405 ***Conclusion***

406 Our study reveals the potential of combined management options focused on improving local habitat
407 quality and the creation of beneficial AES in the surrounding landscape as alternative to the classically
408 considered variables calcareous grassland area and connectivity to ensure the long-term survival of
409 diverse and partially endangered pollinator groups. Future conservation approaches should focus on
410 the preservation of calcareous grassland fragments with attention to area and quality to counteract
411 pollinator species decline through habitat loss and ecosystem decay. In practice, however, it is often
412 not possible to increase the calcareous grassland area or connectivity in order to improve pollinator
413 richness. This study shows that an adapted landscape management and an improvement of habitat
414 quality, especially of nesting sites, can be an effective and more feasible method for pollinator
415 conservation. The configuration of agriculture and agri-environmental schemes in the surrounding
416 landscape favors pollinators not only within the agricultural matrix but even in embedded high-value
417 habitats. Small fields and organically managed crops support the conservation of different wild
418 pollinator groups, including endangered species, in protected high-value habitats like calcareous
419 grasslands by providing additional flower and nesting resources at the landscape scale. Nonetheless,
420 more efforts to expand the area and connectivity of high value habitats will be necessary to mitigate

421 extinction debts in fragmented habitats [68] and ensure the long-term preservation of pollinator
422 richness in human-modified landscapes.

423 **Ethics.** Permission to enter nature conservation areas and to collect wild pollinators was granted by the nature
424 conservation authorities of Lower Franconia (permit number RUF-55.1.2-8646.7-4-42-8 issued by government
425 of Lower Franconia) and Upper Franconia (permit number 55.1-8622 issued by the government of Upper
426 Franconia).

427 **Data availability.** All datasets and the R code supporting this article have been made publicly available at the
428 Dryad Digital Repository (<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.dncjxsm90>) [89].

429 **Declaration of AI use.** We have not used AI-assisted technologies in creating this article.

430 **Authors' contributions.** C.B.: formal analysis, investigation, methodology, writing—original draft, writing—
431 review and editing; A.H.: conceptualization, methodology, writing—review and editing; B.J.: investigation,
432 writing—review and editing; D.S.: formal analysis, writing—review and editing; J.K.: conceptualization,
433 methodology, writing—review and editing; J.Z.: data curation, writing—review and editing; I.S.D.:
434 conceptualization, methodology, writing—review and editing.

435 All authors contributed significantly to revisions and gave final approval for publication.

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441

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